

Study for the Assessment of the Medication Adherence to Oral Hypoglycaemic Drugs in Adults with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, at a Tertiary Care Hospital in Nuh, Haryana

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Abstract:

Introduction: Type II diabetes (DM II) is becoming an epidemic in India with more than 62 million diagnosed diabetics and an increase of nearly 2 million per year.¹ Poor adherence to medication regimens increases the probability of adverse outcomes in type 2 diabetes patients. Therefore, improving medication adherence is a growing priority in controlling this epidemic. Hence, this study was conducted to determine the level of adherence to medication in Type II diabetic patients and to study the various factors affecting medication adherence.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted at the medicine outpatient department (OPD) of a tertiary care teaching hospital, in Nuh Haryana among 172 type II diabetic patients for 1 year using a validated structured predesigned proforma and a validated structured scale The Medication Compliance Questionnaire (MCQ) was used to measure adherence to oral hypoglycaemic drugs.

Results: A total of 172 participants were included. About 54.65% were males, 87.21% were married, 76.75% were from rural areas, 44.19% had formal education, and 65.70% were unemployed. Medication adherence was seen in 33% participants while 65% were not adherent.

Conclusion: The prevalence of medication adherence was 33%. There is a need to improve adherence among type 2 diabetes patients.

Keywords: Medical adherence, Oral hypoglycemic drugs, Type 2 diabetes, Patient compliance, Glycemic control, Diabetes management, Adherence rates, Therapeutic outcomes, Electronic monitoring, Adherence factors, Diabetes treatment, Self-management, Chronic disease.

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Introduction

Diabetes Mellitus is one of the most common non-communicable diseases of the present time in developed countries as well as in developing countries like India. Type II diabetes (DM II) is becoming an epidemic in India with more than 62 million diagnosed diabetics and an increase of nearly 2 million per year. [1] Poor adherence to medication regimens increases the probability of adverse outcomes in type 2 diabetes patients.

Diabetes manifests as a metabolic and vascular syndrome characterised primarily by insulin

resistance, coupled with varying degrees of insulin secretory defects. The micro- and macrovascular complications of the disease, which raise morbidity and mortality, are the primary reason for the true burden of the illness. Maintaining good glycaemic control can help lower the chance of developing these complications. Medication non-adherence reduces both the medication's effectiveness and the glycaemic control it produces. Additionally, it is still necessary to evaluate the degree of medication and self-care adherence among diabetics in the

community as well as the factors that contribute to non-adherence to these practices. [2]

The main treatment goal of diabetes patients is to maintain glycaemic control and prevent diabetes-related complications, morbidities and mortality. That's why agencies such as ICMR, the American Diabetes Association (ADA), and the European Association for the Study of Diabetes (EASD) are currently recommending exercise and dietary modifications, along with oral hypoglycaemic (OHA) drugs, as first-line treatments for improving glycaemic control, thereby preventing both micro-vascular and macro-vascular complications.

Diabetes, if left untreated can cause serious health issues, such as cardiovascular disease, stroke, chronic kidney disease, foot ulcers, damage to the eyes, and prolonged kidney ailment. However, sub-optimal management of patients leads to treatment failure and complications. As of now, there's still no cure for diabetes, and patients must adhere to a healthy lifestyle and timely medication to keep their blood glucose levels in check (glycaemic control). [3,4]

Medication adherence, according to The World Health Organization (WHO), is defined as, "The extent to which a person's behaviour (including medication-taking) aligns with agreed recommendations from a healthcare provider." [5] It encompasses the start of treatment, the implementation of the prescribed regimen, and the termination of medication." It is an essential component of patient treatment and is required to meet clinical objectives.

WHO states in a 2003 report on medication adherence, "Increasing the effectiveness of adherence measures may have a considerably greater impact on the health of the community than any improvement in specific medical treatment." However, it has been shown that 50% - 60% of patients with chronic diseases are non-adherent to the prescribed medications. Therefore, as a result, medication non-adherence accounts for more than 30% of all medicine-related hospital admissions. [6]

There is a paucity of medication adherence studies on Oral Hypoglycaemic drugs (OHAs) in Type II diabetes mellitus adult patients in the Mewat Region. Thus the status of adherence is not readily available. Therefore, the study aimed to assess the medication adherence of oral hypoglycaemic drugs in Type II diabetes mellitus adult patients.

Aim: To assess the medication adherence of oral hypoglycaemic drugs in Type II diabetes mellitus adult patients.

Methodology

Study area: The study was carried out in the OPD Pharmacy/OPD Medicine Department of Shaheed Hasan Khan Mewati Government Medical College, Nalhar, Nuh. This is a 600-bed hospital affiliated with Pandit Bhagwat Dayal Sharma University of Health Sciences Rohtak.

Study Design: This was a non-interventional (observational), cross-sectional, single-centred hospital-based study.

Study Period: This was a 12-month-long study; starting after receiving approval from the IEC for the study.

Target Population: Adult type II Diabetics Mellitus OPD patients.

Study Population: Based on the Inclusion and Exclusion criteria as mentioned below:

Inclusion Criteria

1. Established Type II diabetes mellitus patient on oral hypoglycaemic drugs for at least 1 month visiting the OPD Pharmacy/ OPD medicine department of SHKM GMC.
2. Type II diabetes mellitus patient with oral hypoglycaemic therapy having age > 18 Years of age.
3. Who is willing to give written informed consent?

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with other types of diabetes.
2. Type II diabetic patients on injectables.
3. Participants with cognitive impairment and psychiatric illness.
4. Critically ill patients.
5. Pregnant and lactating women.
6. Patients who are not willing to give written informed consent.

Sampling and Sample Size: Sampling was done by Simple Random Sampling using appropriate software. From the previous study, the prevalence of Medication Adherence to Oral Hypoglycaemic drugs in type II diabetic Mellitus patients is about 40% [7] with 8 % absolute precision, 95% confidence level and 20% non-response proportion, we will require a sample size of 172.

So, the sample size is calculated by using the formula $n = Z^2 p * q / 64 + 20\% = 172$

$$\{n = Z^2 pq = 3.84 * 40 * 60 / 64 = 144 + 20\% = 172\}$$

Source of Data: Data was collected from Face-to-face interviews of the subjects and their medical records by using a validated structured pre-designed proforma.

Study tool: A validated structured pre-designed proforma was used, which contains 4 Sections.

1. Socio-demographic characteristics of type II diabetic patients were included such as Age, Sex, occupation, education, and marital status, area of residence.
2. Medication Data of Oral hypoglycaemic drugs such as name, dosage forms, frequency, total number of drugs and duration will be taken.
3. A validated structured scale The Medication Compliance Questionnaire (MCQ) was used to measure adherence to Oral Hypoglycaemic drugs.
4. This questionnaire has seven questions and assesses patient's intentional and unintentional

nonadherence to medication instructions including reasons for nonadherence. A 4-point Likert scale for each question was used in the data collection tools: The response "Never" was given a score of 4; "sometimes (one to four times per month)", a score of 3; "Often (more than five times per month or more than two times per week)", a score of 2; "Always", a score of 1. Each patient's total score was calculated, ranging from 7 (minimum) to 28 (maximum). Adherence was defined as a score of 27 or more while non-adherence was defined by a score less than 27.

Medication Compliance Questionnaire

Medication Compliance Questionnaire.	1	2	3	4	Total Score
1. How often do you forget to take your medicine?					
2. How often do you decide not to take your medicine?					
3. How often do you miss taking your medicine because you feel better?					
4. How often do you decide to take less of your medicine?					
5. How often do you stop taking your medicine because you feel sick due to side effects of the medicine?					
6. How often do you forget to bring along your medicine when you travel away from home?					
7. How often do you do not take your medicine because you run out of it home?					

The Medication Compliance Questionnaire (MCQ) is a free tool that has been previously validated for assessing medication adherence in previous studies and used by different authors worldwide in their studies. [8]

Human participant protection: Ethics committee approval and written informed consent from participants was obtained.

Data Management and Statistical Analysis: The presentation of the Categorical variables was done in the form of number and percentage (%). The data entry was done in the Microsoft EXCEL spreadsheet and the final analysis was done with the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software, IBM manufacturer, Chicago, USA, version 25.0.

Results and Observations: The study was conducted among OPD patients of SHKM, GMC, Nuh, Haryana. A total of 172 patients were included in the study.

The data was collected from November 2022 to October 2023. The observations of the study are as follows –

A total of 172 Type II diabetes mellitus patients participated in the cross-sectional study.

Age-wise distribution of the patients was analysed and it was found that the maximum number of patients were in the age group of 50-59 (30.23%) followed by the age group of 60-69 (29.07%) (Table 1 & Figure 1). Males 94 (54.65%) outnumbered the female patients 78 (45.35%). (Table 2 & Figure 2)

Table 1: Characteristics of patients

Age(years)	Frequency	Percentage
< 40	15	8.72%
40 to 49	32	18.60%
50 to 59	52	30.23%
60 to 69	50	29.07%
>=70	23	13.37%
Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	78	45.35%
Male	94	54.65%
Residence	Frequency	Percentage
Rural	132	76.75%
Urban	40	23.20%
Education	Frequency	Percentage

Illiterate	96	55.81%
Educated	76	44.19%
Marital status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	150	87.21%
Single	4	2.33%
Widowed	4	2.33%
Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Unemployed	113	65.70%
Non-Professional	29	16.86%
Professional	18	10.47%
Retired	12	6.98%
Lifestyle Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Follow recommended diet control	62	36.05%
Exercise	23	13.37%
Smoking Status	45	26.16%
Consuming paan	1	0.58%
Consuming tobacco	4	2.33%
Consuming alcohol	12	6.98%

Assessment of Medication adherence: The Medication Compliance Questionnaire was used to assess medication adherence in the study. This tool allowed researchers to record and evaluate how well participants adhered to their prescribed medications. A score of 27 was considered adherence. [8] Given the necessity for strict glycaemic control, the medications needed to be adhered to ensure

effective treatment. The average score was, Mean + SD: 22.1 + 4.92. There were 33.14 % (n=172) of patients who were categorized as adherent and 66.86 % were non-adherent.

A low frequency of adherence was noted in the present study. Higher levels of adherence were observed with patients who are currently employed or retired.

Table 2: Age Group Associated with Medication Adherence.

Age(years)	# Adherent	% Adherent	# Non-Adherent	% Non-Adherent
<40	5	33%	10	67%
40 to 49	10	31%	22	69%
50 to 59	18	35%	33	65%
60 to 69	16	32%	35	68%
>=70	8	35%	15	65%

Figure 2: Age Group Associated with Medication Adherence

Figure 2: Out of 172 patients, 35% (18) patients from the 50-59 age group were adherent, followed by 35% (8) from the >70 years age group were adherent, followed by 33% (5) in less than 40-year-old patients, followed by 32%(16) adherence seen in the age group of 60-69 years old, followed by 31% (10) adherence seen in 40-49 year olds.

Table 3: Distribution of Gender with Medication Adherence

Gender	# Adherent	% Adherent	# Non-Adherent	% Non-Adherent
Female	25	32%	53	68%
Male	32	34%	62	66%

Figure 3: Gender Associated with Medication Adherence

Figure 3 Out of 172 patients, 32% (25) females were adherent, while 34% (32) males were adherent.

Table 4: Education Associated with Medication Adherence.

Education	# Adherent	% Adherent	# Non-Adherent	% Non-Adherent
Un-Educated	26	27%	60	93%
Educated	31	41%	45	59%

Figure 5: Education Associated with Medication Adherence

Figure 5 Out of 172 patients, 27% (26) un-educated patients were adherent, while 41% (31) of educated patients were adherent.

Table 6: Area of Residence Associated with Medication Adherence.

Area of Residence	# Adherent	% Adherent	# Non-Adherent	% Non-Adherent
Rural	39	30%	93	70%
Urban	18	45%	22	55%

Figure 6: Area of Residence Associated with Medication Adherence

Figure 6 Out of 172 patients, 30% (39) patients from rural areas were adherent, while 45% (18) patients from urban areas were adherent.

Table 7: Occupation Associated with Medication Adherence.

Occupation	# Adherent	% Adherent	# Non-Adherent	% Non-Adherent
Unemployed	34	30%	79	70%
Non-Professional	8	28%	21	72%
Professional	11	61%	7	39%
Retired	4	33%	6	67%

Figure 7: Occupation Associated with Medication Adherence

Figure 7: Out of 172 patients, 30% (34) unemployed, 28% (8) non-professional, 61.11 % (11) professional patients, 33% (4) retired patients were adherent.

Table 8: Diet Control Associated with Medication Adherence.

Diet Control	# Adherent	% Adherent	# Non-Adherent	% Non-Adherent
No	18	16%	92	84%
Yes	39	63%	23	37%

Figure 8: Distribution of patients according to following the recommended diet, Associated with Medication Adherence

Figure 8: Out of 172 patients, 63% (39) patients who followed the recommended diet were adherent, while 16% (18) patients who didn't follow the recommended diet were adherent.

Table 9: Exercise Associated with Medication Adherence.

Exercise	# Adherent	% Adherent	# Non-Adherent	% Non-Adherent
No	40	27%	109	73%
Yes	17	74%	6	26%

Figure 9: Exercise Associated with Medication Adherence

Figure 9: Out of 172 patients, 74% (17) patients who followed exercise routine were adherent, while 27% (40) patients who didn't follow any exercise routine were adherent.

Table 10: Smoking Associated with Medication Adherence.

Smoking	# Adherent	% Adherent	# Non-Adherent	% Non-Adherent
No	50	40%	76	60%
Yes	6	13%	39	87%

Figure 10: Smoking Associated with Medication Adherence

Figure 10: Out of 172 patients, 13% (6) patients who smoke were adherent, while 40% (51) patients who are non-smokers were adherent.

Table 16: Alcohol consumption Associated with Medication Adherence

Alcohol consumption	# Adherent	% Adherent	# Non-Adherent	% Non-Adherent
No	56	35%	104	65%
Yes	1	8%	11	92%

Figure 11: Alcohol consumption Associated with Medication Adherence

Figure 11: Out of 172 patients, 33% (1) patients who consumes alcohol were adherent, while 35% (56) patients who do not consume alcohol were adherent.

Discussion

Many patients with chronic illnesses, such as Type II Diabetes Mellitus, struggle to adhere to their prescribed drug treatment regimens. To address this issue, a study was conducted to measure adherence to OHA medications in T2DM patients receiving treatment at SHKM GMC, Nuh, Haryana.

In this study of the diabetic population (n=172) receiving treatment at SHKM GMC, the level of medication adherence to oral hypoglycaemic agents (OHAs) was observed to be on the lower side. Oral hypoglycemic adherence among the studied cohort was low, i.e. 33%. This finding indicates a significantly high level of non-adherence to prescribed anti-diabetic regimes among the study cohort. A possible explanation for this observation might be a potential lack of awareness (importance) in the study participants (local people) towards their disease, in terms of diabetes as a disease and complications associated with it if left untreated; hence, not realizing the importance of being adherent to their OHA medication regimens. (Patients encountering reluctance to take medication and comply with treatment).

In the present study, we estimated low adherence, the proportion of adherence was 33% comparable with M Kishorepandi et al [13] who reported it as

32.1%. However, In contrast to study conducted by, Mishra A et al [15] where adherence was reported to be 67.1%, conducted by All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, India, A possible explanation for the high levels of adherence, might be that the study had a predominantly urban population, where the patients have better access to health-care facilities and the majority of the patients were educated 70.54%. And also, the differences observed could also be due to differences in study settings and adherence scales used.

In our study involving 172 patients, we observed a slight male preponderance, with 56.4% of participants being male. Our findings align with the results from studies conducted by Sahoo et al [16]. However, in a study conducted in Tanzania by Doya et al [18], contrasting results emerged the percentage of female participants was significantly higher than their male counterparts, accounting for 70.2%.

Age-wise distribution of the patients was analysed, and it was found that the maximum number of patients were in the age group of 50-59 (30.23%) followed by the age group of 60-69 (29.07%). These findings were similar to the findings of study conducted by Doya et al [18] and were in contrast to the findings of the study conducted by Aravindrashan et al [14] which showed that the maximum participants belonged to 61 - 75 years age group (59.6%) followed by 46-60 years age group (31.2%). In our study of 172 patients, 132 (76.75%) participants were rural residents which contrast to

the findings of studies conducted by Sahoo et al [16] where only 27.8% of patients were from rural areas. In our research, only 76 participants (44.19%) had received formal education. The reason could be that our tertiary care teaching hospital is located in Mewat, a rural part of Haryana, according to the reports of Niti Ayog in 2018, which declared Mewat as the most backward district of entire India based on 49 indicators among 5 sectors an average literacy rate of just 54.06%. The assessment was based on 49 indicators across 5 sectors, revealing an average literacy rate of just 54.06% [22]. The results were in alignment with the study conducted by Yuvaraj K et al [23] where 40% of participants had formal education. However, the findings were in contrast to the study done by Aravindrashan et al [14] where 98.7% of patients had some form of formal education.

In our study of 172 patients, 150 (87.21%) of the patients were married. The study conducted by Sahoo et al [16] comprised of a similar result. Among 172 patients, 65.70% of patients were unemployed, these results were nearly similar to the study conducted by Yuvaraj K et al [23]. The results of the studies conducted by Doya et al [22] were in contrast to the study where 60.9% were employed. Adherence was observed among the retired and professional patients. In the context of Type II diabetes, both employment and medication adherence play crucial roles in managing the condition effectively, as being employed provides financial stability. A possible explanation for this observation might be that employment or work often establishes a structured daily routine and discipline, which might lead to social interactions with individuals or colleagues having more awareness and knowledge about health as a concept and its importance, thereby positively impacting overall health and creating more awareness about medication adherence.

Conclusion

This study synthesized evidence about the level of OHA adherence in type II diabetics in the population of Mewat. Our study showed that medication adherence remained suboptimal in Mewat, consistent with the findings in other regions in India. It is the need of the hour to emphasise medication adherence in diabetes mellitus patients, particularly elderly patients, and their caregivers, which can lead to good glycaemic control, thereby reducing morbidity and mortality among diabetes mellitus patients.

The strength of this study: This is a maiden study on medication adherence conducted in the Department of Pharmacology at SHKM Government Medical College. The prospective design of the study of the patients allowed a more reliable recording of the medication history and the assessment of medication adherence with the use of

standard scales. Our research was conducted at the largest tertiary care teaching hospital in Mewat, which according to Niti Ayog in 2018, declared Mewat as the most backward district of entire India. [24]

These findings serve as essential baseline data for comparison with similar studies at the state, national, and international levels. Furthermore, they will inform future research within our institution. Our study had adequate study duration (12 months): Several studies that were previously conducted had shorter study periods, which can lead to confounding and overestimation of use prevalence.

Limitation of this study

This was a single – a centred study, the findings may not be representative of broader populations or diverse settings. The high prevalence of poor glycaemic control observed in this study may overstate the true situation. This exaggeration could be attributed to the data being collected exclusively from patients attending a hospital, potentially introducing selection bias. Diabetes medication adherence was assessed based on a self-report measure rather than by using objective measures of adherence, and it may be overestimated or non-reflective of actual medication use due to recall biases and social desirability.

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